

Hybrid Computing Based Hardware and Power Efficient Minimum Phase Filter Bank for Audiogram matching in Digital Hearing Aids

Mahesh V V¹, Suresh Kumar A V², Deepthi P M³ Jyothi K⁴

^{1,2,3}College of Engineering Trikaripur, Kasaragod, Kerala

Abstract

A compact hearing aid design requires a filter bank with simple structure that provides audiogram matching for a specific hearing loss pattern. The complexity and delay of reported fixed and reconfigurable filter banks are relatively large. In this paper, a constrained least square, minimum phase finite impulse response filter bank with low hardware complexity and group delay is proposed. Minimum phase FIR filter shows smallest passband group delay in the family of stable filters with the same magnitude response characteristics and the number of coefficients required for filter design is only half of that of the prototype finite impulse response filter. Low group delay has a great impact on envelope fidelity, which is a primary factor in determining the intelligibility of speech. Three methods using hybrid arithmetic are proposed here to implement the filter bank structure. In the first method, floating point arithmetic is used to realize filter bank. In the second method, hardware complexity is reduced by using stochastic computation for multiplication operation. Area and power requirement is further reduced in the third method by the multiplexer based stochastic computation method. Synthesis results presented justifies the theoretical claims in the design.

Keywords:

constrained least square method, minimum phase, finite impulse response filter bank, stochastic computing, audiogram

1. INTRODUCTION

Filter bank has a critical role in the digital hearing aid design and it separates the audio spectrum into different bands to best compensate hearing loss. Review of World Health Organization shows that millions are suffering from hearing loss problem and a considerable percentage of the affected persons are in the under developed countries. So low cost hearing aid devices are still a need of the day and to achieve this, hardware complexity of the device should be minimized. In this paper, a constrained least square minimum phase approach is used to design finite impulse response filter bank structure suitable for hearing aids with reduced hardware complexity and low passband group delay. The sensitivity of a hearing impaired person is low for certain frequency bands. In digital hearing aids, microphone signals are passed through a set of filters and subband filter gains are adjusted to compensate the audiogram of hearing impaired person. More than 10 ms delay in the device will result in a disturbing effect for hearing aid users. Minimization of hardware requirement, power consumption and delay are the important design considerations of a compact digital hearing aid.

Uniform and nonuniform filterbanks are generally used for the design for digital hearing aids. Nonuniform filter banks are more suitable for digital hearing aids as human ear shows nonuniform frequency resolution characteristics. Filter bank with Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) structure has low computation complexity but filter bank with Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter is preferred due to linear phase characteristic, stability and regular structure of the system. Design and implementation of low-power ANSI S1.11 filter bank for digital hearing aids is reported in [1]. Long group delay due to the multirate structure and stringent filter specifications are the main drawbacks of this system. Users will be disturbed if the hearing aid delay is more than 10 ms. FIR reconfigurable filter bank with reduced computational complexity is presented in [2] in which decimation, interpolation and frequency response masking methods are used. Here the hardware complexity is reduced at the price of longer delay, greater than 20ms. Long delays will cause many problems such as the difference between aid generated and direct received sound, etc.

A nonlinear transformation based reconfigurable filter bank is proposed in [3] by Huang et al. Variable bandwidth digital filter based on Farrow structure for hearing aid application is proposed in [4], in which the precision of Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic is compromised to reduce hardware complexity. In this case, additional accumulator circuitry is required for applying tunable factor value to the system and which will result in further increase in system complexity. A reconfigurable filter bank based on symmetry property of linear phase filter and fractional interpolation is reported in [5]. A nonuniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) filter bank is proposed in [6] in which filter orders are different for different bands. A constrained least square (CLS) FIR filter bank for audiogram matching in hearing aids is presented in [7], in which multiplier requirement is large as the order of filter used is high. Fractional interpolation technique is utilized to generate filter banks in [8]. In this method hardware complexity is reduced at the expense of increase in delay up to 12.9 ms. Reconfigurable filter bank for hearing aid applications with IoT is proposed in [9]. Frequency warping and cosine modulation techniques are used for the filter bank design in [10]. Hardware complexity and delay are comparatively low in this design.

Error tolerant capacity and less area requirement are the key features of stochastic computing (SC) and which makes it preferable for many computation intensive applications [11]. Hardware requirement can be reduced considerably in realizing the image processing systems by using SC [12]. Constraints in accuracy and long processing delay are the common issues associated with SC applications [13]. Stochastic computing

based compact digital filter is presented in [14] by H.Ichihara et al. Synthesis of correlated stochastic bit streams for specified probabilities is discussed in [15]. In [16], stochastic computation based asymmetric filters for audio signal processing is reported. Stochastic computation based area and energy efficient Gammatone filter is reported in [17]. Area and power efficient filter bank structure using modified stochastic computing is reported in [18].

Literature review shows that, it is not easy to trade off between hardware complexity and delay of filter banks for hearing aid devices. In this work, a stable minimum phase filter derived from constrained least square (CLS) FIR filter, suitable for hearing aid applications is proposed. The number of coefficients in a minimum phase filter is only half of that of the prototype FIR filter. So hardware complexity of the filter is reduced without any effect on magnitude response characteristics.

Minimum phase filters are inherently stable because all poles of the system are always inside the unit circle. Passband group delay of minimum phase filter is very much small compared to that of linear phase FIR filter with the same characteristics. This property of minimum phase filter helps to preserve the envelope fidelity of speech signal. In a noisy environment, envelope fidelity is a key factor in determining the intelligibility and quality of speech [19]. Minimum phase filter exhibit minor variations in phase in the passband but studies in psychoacoustics has shown that the sensitivity of human ear to such small phase distortions is low. Experiments conducted by Lipshitz et al, reported in [20] states that such minute phase variations on normal music and speech signals are not at all audible.

There are three methods proposed in this work to reduce hardware complexity, delay and power requirement of filter banks for audiogram matching in hearing aids. In the first method, floating point arithmetic is used to implement the minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank. Hardware and power requirement for implementation of filter bank is reduced in the second compared to first method using stochastic computation. Here, only the computation intensive multiplication operation is carried out in stochastic domain. Area and power requirement are further reduced in method 3 compared to method 2, because in this system, stochastic numbers representing input samples are selected from memory by using a multiplexer. The filter bank structures are synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL compiler v11.10 software. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response.

The paper is organized as follows. An overview of minimum phase constrained least square FIR filters is given in Section II. In Section III, basics of stochastic multiplication are discussed. Hearing loss and audiogram are presented in Section IV, Filter bank structure implementation and audiogram matching are given in Section V, performance evaluation is reported in Section VI. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

2. MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

2.1 CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

Constrained least square FIR filter method enables to design FIR filters without explicitly specifying transition bandwidths for the magnitude response. This approach is more suitable for the situations where signal information and noise appear together in the same frequency band. Upper and lower thresholds for maximum allowable ripple in the magnitude response of the filter are defined in this technique [21-23]. Here, least square error minimization technique is applied not only to specific bands but over the whole frequency range of the filter response. The error minimization includes areas of discontinuity present in the ideal filter response. The integral square error includes the region around cut off frequency and thus avoids Gibb's phenomenon without using windowing operation. The frequency response of FIR filter can be represented as

$$H(\omega) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} h(n)e^{-j\omega n} \tag{1}$$

If $h(n) = h(N - 1 - n)$, then $H(\omega)$ has linear phase and can be written as

$$H(\omega) = C(\omega)e^{-jM\omega} \tag{2}$$

where $C(\omega)$ is the real valued amplitude, and $M = \frac{(N-1)}{2}$ for filter of length N . For symmetric odd length filters $C(\omega)$ can be represented as

$$C(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c(0) + \sum_{n=1}^M c(n) \cos n\omega \tag{3}$$

Where the impulse response coefficients $h(n)$, in terms of the cosine coefficients $c(n)$ are

$$h(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} c(M - n) & \text{for } 0 \leq n \leq M - 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} c(0) & \text{for } n = M \\ \frac{1}{2} c(n - M) & \text{for } M + 1 \leq n \leq N - 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Let $D(\omega)$ be the desired amplitude of an ideal lowpass filter. Approximating this discontinuous function by the cosine polynomial $C(\omega)$ is the fundamental filter design problem. The approximation error can be written as

$$E(\omega) = D(\omega) - C(\omega) \tag{5}$$

The primary measures of approximation used in filter design are

- i) The weighted integral square error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_2 = \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi W(\omega) (C(\omega) - D(\omega))^2 d\omega \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

ii) The weighted Chebyshev error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_\infty = \max_{\omega \in [0, \pi]} |W(\omega)(C(\omega) - D(\omega))| \quad (7)$$

where $W(\omega)$ is a nonnegative error weighting function. The simplest method to design optimal FIR filters is to minimize the term $\|C(\omega) - D(\omega)\|_2$.

The CLS FIR filter design minimizes the unweighted integral square error with the constraint that local minima and maxima of $C(\omega)$ lie within the specified lower and upper bound functions $K_L(\omega)$ and $K_U(\omega)$. The lower and upper bound functions are given by

$$K_L(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 - \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ -\delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$K_U(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 + \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ \delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where δ_p and δ_s are the maximum allowed deviations in the passband and stopband. This method of filter design is more suitable for situation where the maximum peak error size is to be controlled and there is no reason to assume that the input signals to be filtered have no energy in the transition band.

2.2 MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

Linear Phase FIR filter with high order has narrow transition band and has very long group delay which is proportional to the filter order. In hearing aid applications, such a long delay is not at all favorable. By the minor relaxation in linear phase characteristics, design of FIR filter with lower order is possible. This will in turn reduce the overall group delay and also reduce the computational cost by saving the number of multipliers required for design. Minimum phase filter group delay has the smallest value among the family of filters with the same magnitude response. A stable causal filter is considered as minimum phase filter if all of its zeros are inside the unit circle [21]. Consider a FIR transfer function of degree M

$$H(z) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(n) z^{-n} \quad (10)$$

The mirror image polynomial of $H(z)$ is given by

$$\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M} H(z^{-1}) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(M-n) z^{-n} \quad (11)$$

The zeros of $\hat{H}(z)$ are reciprocal to that of $H(z)$. As a result

$$K(z) = H(z)\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M} H(z)H(z^{-1}) \quad (12)$$

$K(z)$ has zeros with mirror image symmetry in z plane and is thus a Type I linear phase transfer function with order $2M$. $K(z)$ has double zeros on the unit circle and is thus factorizable to $H(z)$ and $\hat{H}(z)$. From the equation (12), the magnitude squared function can be represented as

$$|H(e^{j\omega})|^2 = K(\omega) \quad (13)$$

Amplitude response of $K(z)$ is thus non negative. It is also clear that, $K(\omega)$ has double zeros on $[0, \pi]$ interval as $K(z)$ has double zeros on the unit circle. Based on this logic a minimum phase filter can be derived by using the following procedure [24, 25]. Step1: Design a Type I linear phase FIR transfer function $E(z)$ of degree $2M$, with the amplitude response $\hat{E}(\omega)$ specifications

$$1 - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$-\delta_s(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq \delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

$E(z)$ has only a single unit circle zero.

Step 2: Determination of the linear phase transfer function

$$K(z) = \delta_s(E) z^{-M} + E(z) \quad (14)$$

Its amplitude response $\hat{K}(\omega)$ satisfies the relation

$$1 + \delta_s(E) - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_s(E) + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$0 \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 2\delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

It is evident that, $K(z)$ has double zeros in the stop band along with all other zeros situated with a mirror image symmetry. Thus $K(z)$ can be expressed as

$$K(z) = z^{-M} H(z)H(z^{-1}) \quad (15)$$

Here $H(z)$ is a minimum phase FIR transfer function which contains the zeros of $K(z)$ that are inside unit circle and one from each of the double zeros of $K(z)$ on the unit circle.

Step3: Use spectral factorization to determine $H(z)$ from $K(z)$.

In the direct method, minimum phase filter is obtained by selecting the zeros of $K(z)$ that are inside the unit circle. The pass band ripple $\delta_p(E)$ and the stop band ripple $\delta_s(E)$ of $E(z)$ have to ensure that the specified pass band ripple δ_p and stop band ripple δ_s of $H(z)$ are satisfied accurately. It can be shown that

$$\delta_p(E) = \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta_p}{1 + \delta_s}} - 1 \quad (16)$$

$$\delta_s(E) = \sqrt{\frac{2\delta_s}{1 + \delta_s}} \quad (17)$$

Non linear IIR filters with smaller group delay can be easily implemented, but such filters are not at all stable. The number of coefficients in a minimum phase filter is reduced to half of that of the prototype FIR filter. Smaller group delay can be

achieved in the passband region by using stable minimum phase FIR filters with low hardware complexity. Minimum phase filters are always stable because all poles of the system are inside the unit circle. In the proposed design constrained least square FIR Filter is used as the prototype FIR filter to derive minimum phase FIR filter.

3. MULTIPLICATION BY STOCHASTIC COMPUTING

Unipolar and bipolar format are used to represent real numbers in stochastic computation. In unipolar format, the input s is a real number in the unit interval ($0 \leq s \leq 1$). For example, a binary input {101} can be represented as stochastic bit stream S , with 5 one bits, out of 16 bits. The stochastic bit streams {1010101010000000}, {1111100000000000}...etc represent the input stream {101}. This stochastic bit stream S , is also interpreted as $s = P(S=1) = 5/16$. The term $P(S)$ represent the probability for a bit to be one in the stream of bits. Multiplication operation is computational intensive in conventional signed binary representation but in SC, it can be performed by using AND gate logic. In unipolar format, a single AND gate is used to perform multiplication operation and is shown in Figure 1. Here the input and output values represents, probabilities of number of bits with value one over the total number of bits in the stream. Accuracy of computation is a function of the correlation of input bit streams and it will decrease with increase in correlation. In the case of long sequences, minor changes in bits will not affect much the probability of ones in the sequence and so increasing number of bits in the stream of representation will improve accuracy. Realization of addition operation in stochastic domain is a little bit complex, so stochastic logic is used only for multiplication operation in the proposed filter bank design. 255 bit long stochastic bit streams in unipolar format are used to represent input samples and filter coefficients in the proposed design. Binary to stochastic converter at input section and stochastic to binary converter at output section of the multiplier are the two important functional blocks in the system.

3.1 STOCHASTIC NUMBER GENERATOR

Linear feedback shift register (LFSR) is commonly used to generate random sequences. LFSR is a sequential circuit that generates finite number of states in a deterministic fashion.

Fig.1 Stochastic multiplication

Fig. 4 Stochastic to binary converter

Fig. 2 Linear feedback shift register

LFSR with 8 bit register used for the proposed design is shown in Figure 2. Working principle of stochastic number generator is in such a way that the output of 8 bit LFSR is compared with the binary input data. Comparator output become one, if LFSR output data is greater than binary input data, otherwise it become zero. Then LFSR data is shifted by one bit position and comparison is again made with the binary input data [18,27]. This process steps are repeated for 255 times to generate a stochastic number of 255 bit length. The functional block diagram of binary to stochastic converter is shown in Figure 3. In the proposed work, filter coefficients in stochastic bit stream format are used to reduce area requirement and only the stochastic numbers corresponding to input samples are calculated instantaneously.

3.2 STOCHASTIC TO BINARY CONVERTER

Stochastic to binary conversion is not difficult as compared to generator and a binary counter performs this function. An 8 bit binary counter is used in the proposed design to convert stochastic number to binary format. Binary counter precisely counts the number of one bit present in the input stochastic bit stream. Block diagram of Stochastic to Binary converter is given in Figure 4.

4. AUDIOGRAM AND HEARING LOSS

Audiometric testing is used to measure the hearing ability of a person and a chart of this measurement is known as Audiogram. The softest sound a person can hear at specific audio frequency band is termed as threshold of hearing. Audiogram of a person with normal level of hearing is shown in Figure 5. Here, Y axis represents the ear response measured in decibels (dB) and corresponding frequency in Hertz (Hz) is plotted in X axis. Generally, thresholds upto 20 dB are treated as normal hearing level. Symbols 'O' and 'X' used in the audiogram represents the response of right ear and left ear respectively. In a standard audiogram, hearing level measurements are usually carried out at octave frequencies (250/500/1k/2k/4k/8k).

Fig. 3 Binary to stochastic converter

A hearing impaired person's sensitivity is low at certain frequency bands and this hearing loss is rectified by the selective amplification of sound signals at the respective band of frequencies. Reference audiograms used in this work are selected from the website of independent hearing aid information source <http://www.earinfo.com>. Response of hearing aid filter bank should match the audiogram of affected patient to compensate the hearing loss by selective amplification of audio signals. Audiograms of mild hearing loss at all frequencies, mild hearing loss at high frequencies and mild to moderate hearing loss at all frequencies are used in this paper for the analysis of hardware complexity, delay and matching error. Matching error is defined as the maximum overall error between filter bank response and the audiogram of a specific hearing loss case. Matching error 3dB is considered as the maximum tolerable limit, because psycho acoustical studies have shown that [20], people are generally not sensitive to errors less than 3dB.

5 CLS FIR FILTER BANK AND AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

CLS FIR filter of order $n = 60$, $\delta_p = 10^{-5}$, $\delta_s = 10^{-5}$ is used as the prototype filter for the design of minimum phase filter bank structure. The smooth transition band characteristic of minimum phase CLS FIR filter enables to reduce filter order and number of bands required for audiogram matching

The individual band widths of 6 filters used for filter bank design are shown in Table 1. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response. Frequency response of low pass minimum phase CLS FIR filter with cut off frequency 4 kHz is shown in Figure 6. Sampling frequency used for the filter design is 16 kHz and maximum pass band group delay of the filter is 9 samples (0.5625 ms). Group delay shows a light variation from 2 to 9 samples (0.125 ms to 0.5625 ms) in the pass band as shown in Figure 7. But this minor phase variations do not affect the hearing perception. Number of coefficient multiplications required is only 31 for minimum phase filter derived from the CLS FIR filter with order 60.

Fig 6. Minimum phase CLS FIR lowpass filter response

Pass band group delay and number of multipliers required for the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter are lower than the reported methods in literature. Audiogram matching for

different filter orders are carried out and is plotted in Figure 8, minimum matching error is obtained for the filter bank structure with filter order 60 (31 coefficients). That is why minimum phase filter derived from CLS FIR filter with order $n = 60$ is

the requirement of large number of multipliers and which is proportional to order of the filter. Here a minimum phase constrained least square FIR filter bank is proposed with simple structure with low computational complexity and pass band group delay.

Fig 7. Group delay of Minimum phase CLS FIR filter lowpass filter

Fig. 8 Matching Errors for different filter orders

Fig. 9 Minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank structure

selected for the design of proposed filter bank. High computational cost and long passband group delay are the two important drawbacks of FIR filter banks. This is mainly due to

The filter bank structure is shown in Figure 9. Initially, sub band gain of the filter bank is taken as the midpoint value of a specific band of audiogram of a particular hearing loss case and then it

is varied to get a minimum overall matching error. In this work, data broadcast structure is used to implement the filter bank, in which signals are transmitted to all the multipliers at the same time. By this structure, critical path can be minimized without pipelining latches and it will in turn improve clock speed of the system [28]. Critical path represents the minimum time required to process a new sample.

5.1 AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

Optimal filter bandwidths are selected by simulating filters individually for a minimum matching error. The stop band attenuation of the minimum phase CLS FIR Filter is 50 dB and the transition bandwidth is 0.106π radians. Filter bank performance is evaluated by Matlab software and the optimum filter gains and frequency bands required for audiogram matching are obtained by a number of simulation trials. In this work, filter banks for matching audiogram patterns of mild hearing loss at all frequencies, mild hearing loss at high frequencies and mild to moderate hearing loss at all frequencies are designed. Generally, communication distance is 12 meter for a person with normal hearing whereas this is reduced to 2 meter for a person suffering from mild hearing loss at all frequencies. The audiogram is plotted in Figure 10(a) and Figure 10(b) shows frequency response of the filter bank. Best matching results are obtained by carefully varying the gain magnitudes of 6 bands as shown in Figure 10(c). Matching error is plotted in Figure 13(a) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.51 dB. Figure 11(a) represents audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies. Frequency response of 6 band filter bank is shown in Figure 11(b), the matching is shown in Figure 11(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 13(b) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.92 dB. Figure 12(a) represents audiogram of a person suffering from mild to

in Figure 12(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 13(c) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.88 dB.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Table 1: Frequency bands used

Hearing loss	No. of bands	Bandwidth (Hz)
Mild hearing loss at all frequencies.	6	300,1040,1900, 2400,1900, 1600
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies.	6	530,1120,1120,1600,1520, 2880
Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies.	6	600,700,3400,2450,2000,1400

moderate hearing loss at low frequencies. Frequency response of filter bank is shown in Figure 12(b), the matching is shown

Fig. 10. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at all frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

Fig. 12. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

5.2 SYNTHESIS OF FILTER BANKS

Filter banks are synthesized in three different ways in the proposed work. Floating point arithmetic is used in the first method to synthesize minimum phase CLS FIR Filter banks and logic of stochastic computing is used in the second method. The long computation delay in stochastic domain is reduced in the proposed method by using an array of 255ANDgates for multiplication operation instead of a single AND gate used in conventional methods. Here a mixed method is used, computational intensive multiplication operation only is performed in stochastic domain and addition operation is performed in the binary domain itself. In the third method, a multiplexer selects the stochastic number stored in memory corresponding to the input sample value. Block diagram of the system is shown in Fig.14. Thus power and hardware requirement are further reduced in this method. Minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank is synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL Compiler v11.10 software. The area, power and delay reports of Filter bank structure for audiogram matching of mild hearing loss at all frequencies are given in Table 2.

Fig. 13. Matching error for the case of (a) Mild hearing loss at all frequencies, (b) Mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (c) Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies

Fig. 14 Binary to stochastic converter using multiplexer

6. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In the proposed methods, hardware requirement for the multiplication operation involved in the filter bank design is reduced considerably. Battery life and size of hearing aid mainly depends on power requirement and area utilization of the filter bank structure used in the device. From the synthesis results of filter bank structures for matching of audiogram for mild hearing loss at all frequencies, it is clear that the percentage savings in area utilization are 20.67% and 20.70 % in proposed method 2 and proposed method 3 respectively compared to proposed method 1. Similarly percentage savings in power are 72.31% and 77.51% in proposed method 2 and proposed method 3 respectively compared to method 1. Stochastic methods suffer accuracy compared to floating

point arithmetic and accuracy can be improved by increasing the length of stochastic bit sequence. Percentage savings in area

generally the minimum number of multipliers required for n^{th} order filter is $(n + 1)$. In the method proposed by Swamy and

Table 2: Synthesis results of Filter bank for Mild hearing loss at all frequencies

	Mahesh [7] (Floating point)	Proposed 1 (Floating point)	Proposed 2 (Stochastic)	Proposed 3 (Stochastic)
Area (μm^2)	44,24,437.99	21,29,824.07	16,89,525.13	16,88,863.18
Power (nW)	513,682,049	242,802,011	67,231,602.9	54,603,494.4
Delay (μS)	4919.40	4290	4317.80	4317.80

Fig. 15 Comparison of (a) Area (b) Power

and power requirement in the proposed method 1 compared to earlier work [7] are 51.86% and 52.73% respectively. So the proposed filter bank structures utilizes less area and consumes low power, thus reduce hearing aid size and increase its battery life. Comparison of area utilization and power requirement is given in Figure 15. The passband group delay of the minimum phase CLS FIR filter used in the proposed method is lower than reported methods. Area utilization and power consumption increases with increase in number of multipliers per filter in the structure. Performance comparison of recently reported filter bank structures used for digital hearing aid design is given in the Table 3. Filter bank designed by Huang et al.[3] is based on non linear transformation and in which the number of multipliers/filter required is 187 and the delay is 7.77 ms. Farrow structure based variable bandwidth filter is reported in [4] in which the number of multipliers required for per filter is 36 and the delay is 2.06 ms. Here precision of Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic is compromised to reduce the multiplier requirement. Fractional interpolation based filter bank proposed in [5], uses 84 multipliers/filter and the delay is 13.5ms. In the filter bank based on non uniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) reported by Sakthivel et al [6], complexity is expressed in terms of filter order and

Alex [9], delay is made less than 10 ms at the expense of increase in matching error, even greater than 4 dB in some cases. Second order frequency warping based filter bank structure by T Ma et al. consists of 73 multipliers and seven bands and the delay of the system is 7.13 ms. In the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank, the number of multipliers per filter is 31 and the maximum pass band group delay is only 0.5625 ms which is the least among the reported methods. Matching error of the proposed structure is within the tolerable limit value of 3 dB. Comparisons shows that the proposed filter bank structure has better performance and the silicon area required for real time implementation can be reduced by the proposed SC based design. Since area, power requirement and delay of the proposed filter bank structure is low, it is suitable for the design of low cost digital hearing aids. The proposed methods can be easily extended to other common types of hearing loss cases also.

6. CONCLUSION

Power efficiency and small size are the two important features of an optimal digital hearing aid. Filter bank structures used in this work utilize less area and consume low power than

the reported methods and thus suitable for the design of compact digital hearing aids. The significant reduction in multiplications per sample enables to reduce hardware requirement considerably in this design. The proposed minimum phase

- Digital Hearing Aids,” *IEEE Trans. on Circuits and Systems*, vol. 57, no.7, July 2010
2. Y. W. and D. Liu, “Reconfigurable Digital filter bank for Hearing Aid Systems with a variety of Sound Wave Decomposition Plans,” *IEEE Trans. on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 60, no.6, June 2013

Table 3: Performance comparison

Hearing Loss	Method	Multipliers/ Filter	No. of bands	Delay (ms)	Matching Error (dB)
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	1.65
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	102	10	3.18	2.2
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	16.5	2.03
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	0.98
	Swamy, Alex [9]	72	21	8.67	4.40
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	2.34
	Proposed	31	6	0.5625	1.92
Mild hearing loss at all frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	1.35
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	56	9	1.75	1.69
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	12	1.49
	Mahesh,Shahana [7]	74	8	2.25	1.82
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	2.42
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	0.95
	Proposed	31	6	0.5625	1.51
Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	3.75
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	29	6	0.87	1.87
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	12	1.48
	Mahesh,Shahana [7]	74	7	2.25	1.61
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	1.08
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	0.98
	Proposed	31	6	0.5625	1.88

constrained least square finite impulse response filter bank show very low pass band group delay and matching error of the filter bank is also within the tolerable limit.

REFERENCES

1. Y. T. Kuo, T. J. Lin, Y. T. Li, C. W. Liu, “Design and Implementation of low-power ANSI S1.11 Filter Bank for
2. S. Huang, L. Tian, X. Ma, Y. Wei, “A reconfigurable sound wave decomposition filter bank for hearing aids based on nonlinear transformation,” *IEEE Biomed. Circ. Syst.*, vol.10, no.2, pp. 487-96, 2016, doi:10.1109/TBCAS.2015.2436916
3. I. Raghu, H. Nisha, E. Elizabeth, “High performance continuous variable bandwidth digital filter design for hearing aid application,” *International journal of*

- Electronics and Communications*, vol.92, pp. 36-53, 2018, doi:10.1016/j.aeue.2018.05.006
5. A. Amir, T. S. Bindiya, E Elizabeth, "Design and implementation of reconfigurable filter bank structure for low complexity hearing aids using 2-level sound wave decomposition," *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 43, pp. 96-109, May 2018, doi:10.1016/j.bspc.2018.02.020
 6. V. Sakthivel, E. Elizabeth, "Design of hardware-efficient digital hearing aids using non-uniform MDFT filter banks," *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, vol.12, pp. 1429-1436, 2018, doi:10.1007/s11760-017-1225-1
 7. V. V. Mahesh, T K Shahana, "Constrained least square non uniform dynamic filter bank for delay and hardware efficient digital hearing aids," *Health and Technology*, vol.9, pp. 355-363, 2019, doi:10.1007/s12553-018-0268-9
 8. Devis T, Manual M, "A low complexity 3 level filter bank design for effective restoration of audibility in digital hearing aids" *Biomed. Eng. Lett.*, vol.10(4), pp. 593-601, July 29,2020, doi: 10.1007/s13534-020-00167-4.
 9. Swamy, K.A., Alex, Z.C. "Efficient low delay reconfigurable filter bank using parallel structure for hearing aid applications with IoT". *Pers Ubiquit Comput* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00779-021-01600-w>
 10. T. Ma, Y. Wei and X. Lou, "Reconfigurable Nonuniform Filter Bank for Hearing Aid Systems," in *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 30, pp. 758-771, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TASLP.2021.3138713.
 11. A. Alaghi, J. P. Hayes, "Survey of Stochastic computing,"
 12. *ACM Trans. Embed. Comput. Syst.*, vol.12, no.2, 2013
 13. P. Li, D.J. Lilja, W. Qian, K. Basargan, M.D. Riedel "Computation on stochastic bit streams , *Digital Image Processing , Case studies*," *IEEE Trans. VLSI*, vol.22, pp. 449-462, Mar. 2014
 14. Y. Liu and K. K. Parhi, "Architectures for recursive digital filters using stochastic computing," *IEEE Trans. Signal Processing* , vol.64, pp. 3705-3718, Jul. 2016 doi: 10.1109/TSP.2016.2552513.
 15. H. Ichihara, T. Sugino, S. Ishii, T. Iwagaki, T. Inoue, "Compact and Accurate digital filters based on stochastic computing," *IEEE Trans. Emerging topics in Comp.*vol,99, pp.1-10, 2016
 16. Y. Liu, Megha, K. K. Parhi, "Synthesis of correlated bit streams for stochastic computing," *Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers*, 2016, *IEEE Xplore*, doi : 10.1109/ACSSC.2016.7869017
 17. N. Onizava, S. Koshita, "Design of Stochastic Asymmetric Compensation Filters for Auditory Signal Processing," *IEEE Global SIP* 2017, doi: 10.1109/GlobalSIP.2017.8309174
 18. N. Onizava, S. Koshita, S. Sakamoto, "Area/energy efficient Gammatone filters based on Stochastic computation," *IEEE Trans. VLSI*, vol.25, no.10, 2017
 19. V. V. Mahesh, T. K. Shahana, "Design and synthesis of Filter Banks using area and power efficient stochastic computing," *IEEE World conference on smart trends in systems, security and sustainability* 2020, London, pp. 662-666, doi: 10.1109/WorldS450073.2020.9210403
 20. K. Arehart , P. Souza , J. Kates, M. S. Pedersen, "Relationship among signal fidelity, Hearing loss, and working memory for digital noise suppression," *Ear and Hearing*, , vol.36, no. 5, pp 505 -516, Sept. 2015, doi : 10.1097/AUD.000000000000173
 21. Lipshitz, P. Stanley, Pocock, Mark, Vanderkooy, John, "On the Audibility of Midrange Phase Distortion in Audio Systems," *JAES*, vol.30, no.9, pp. 580-595, Sept. 1982.
 22. I. W. Sclesnick, M. Lang and C. S. Burrus, "Constrained Least Square Design of FIR Filters without specified Transition Bands," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing*, vol.44, no.8, Aug. 1996.
 23. I. W. Sclesnick, M. Lang and C S. Burrus, "Modified Algorithm for constrained Least Square Design of multi band FIR Filters without specified Transition Bands," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing*, vol. 46, no.2 , pp. 497 - 501, Feb. 1998
 24. V. V. Mahesh, T. K. Shahana, "Delay and Area Efficient Sound Wave Decomposition by Nonuniform Filter Bank for Digital Hearing Aids," *SAI Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys)* 2016, ISBN 978-319-56994-9, *Lecture notes in Networks and Systems*, Springer
 25. O. Herrmann, H. W. Schuessler, "Design of non recursive Filters with minimum phase," *Electron. Lett*, vol. 6(11), pp. 329-330, May 1970.
 26. S. K. Mitra, *Digital Signal Processing, 3rd ed*, Tata McGraw Hill, 2008
 27. P. K. Gupta, R. Kumaresan, "Binary multiplication with PN sequences," *IEEE Trans. Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, vol.36, no.4, pp. 603-606,1988
 28. K. K. Parhi, *VLSI Digital Signal processing systems, Design and implementation*, Wiley India, 2011